

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Activation of transposases by HPV16E5.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

Citations

1. Ren, S., Gaykalova, D.A., Guo, T., Favorov, A.V., Fertig, E.J., Tamayo, P., Callejas-Valera, J.L., Allevato, M., Gilardi, M., Santos, J. and Fukusumi, T., 2020. HPV E2, E4, E5 drive alternative carcinogenic pathways in HPV positive cancers. *Oncogene*, 39(40), pp.6327-6339.